

THE ROLE OF COMMUNICATIVE METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH IN HIGHER
EDUCATION

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Abstract. This article examines the role of communicative methods in teaching English in higher education. It highlights the main principles of communicative language teaching, important classroom techniques, and their influence on students’ participation, confidence, and practical language use. The article also discusses common classroom challenges and suggests simple ways to overcome them effectively.

Keywords. communicative methods, English language teaching, higher education, communicative competence, student-centered learning, classroom interaction

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada oliy ta’limda ingliz tilini o’qitishda kommunikativ metodlarning o’rni tahlil qilinadi. Unda kommunikativ til o’qitishning asosiy tamoyillari, muhim sinf metodlari hamda ularning talabalarning faolligi, ishonchi va amaliy til qo’llash ko’nikmalariga ta’siri yoritiladi. Shuningdek, maqolada ta’lim jarayonida uchraydigan asosiy muammolar va ularni bartaraf etishning sodda hamda samarali yo’llari ko’rsatib beriladi.

Kalit so’zlar. kommunikativ metodlar, ingliz tilini o’qitish, oliy ta’lim, kommunikativ kompetensiya, talaba markazli ta’lim, sinfdagi o’zaro muloqot

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается роль коммуникативных методов в преподавании английского языка в высшем образовании. Освещаются основные принципы коммуникативного обучения, важные методы работы в аудитории и их влияние на активность студентов, уверенность и практическое использование языка. Также в статье анализируются распространённые трудности в учебном процессе и предлагаются простые и эффективные пути их преодоления.

Ключевые слова. Коммуникативные методы, преподавание английского языка, высшее образование, коммуникативная компетенция, студентоориентированное обучение, аудиторное взаимодействие

Introduction

These days, it is visible that higher education instructors and students do not rely much on the grammar rules, memorization, and translation. That’s why, their language learning process goes on smoothly and productively. At present, students mostly, require the language for the purpose of researching, studying, communicating, and future professional life. For this reason, English lessons should help and support learners to use the language in meaningful and contextual situations. With these methods, students can communicate, collaborate, and express their views and interact with others as much as they can in this target language.

In modern language teaching field, the most important and effective method is the communicative approach, as it helps them a lot in different jobs. This method is like a interaction tool for the learners and this method only uses the language which is connected to real life and it is the combination of realistic world contexts.

This approach does not rely a lot on the grammar rules, so learners do not have to pay much attention the fixed rules, rather they can learn them while communicating and interacting with real people and in real life contexts. This is also considered the quickest and simplest way of acquiring the language. By applying this method, students can be more independent especially, in the academic field because they should be more active and competent during the lessons mainly in practical classes.

In a nutshell, this article identifies the necessity of communicative methods in university life and how these methods can enhance instructors’ teaching quality and students’ learning outcomes.

Theoretical basis of communicative teaching

The main goal and purpose of language learning in communicative language teaching is communicative competence. This means that students can use the language properly and apply it in different contexts, express their ideas clearly and comprehensibly, understand the meaning, and respond to people in different topics. So, the language is not only knowing the grammar and using it for accuracy, but also it is connected to interaction, fluency, and confidence of learners’ use. In a communicative classroom, language is seen as a tool for social interaction and connection. The instructor creates contexts and opportunities for students to share their ideas, describe experiences, discuss problems, and collaborate with each other in order to communicate better. This way helps learners connect language forms with meaning and practice English in a natural way.

This approach changes the role of the teacher in a great way because in a traditional class main attention is on the teacher not the students. However, in the communicative teaching classroom, main focus is on the students and they should be more active and interact a lot. The communicative approach also changes the role of the teacher. In a traditional classroom, the teacher often explains while students mainly listen and repeat. In communicative teaching, the teacher becomes a facilitator, organizer, and monitor. Students take a more active role in the lesson and become responsible participants in learning.

Main communicative methods used in higher education

Communicative teaching involves several important and effective techniques for learners, mainly, in higher education students including, role play, discussions, presentations, project work, pair work and group work. These techniques are quite productive if they are used and implemented in a true way. Pair work is a simple and quite effective way because it provides each student opportunity to speak and connect with others. In some classes, there are quite a lot of students, in that situation it looks like quite difficult to appeal all students to the interaction especially with their partners. Pair work improves and increases students’ involvement a lot, since it creates more time for speaking. This method also enhances the knowledge of shy and introverted students.

Group work is very important for more complex and longer tasks so that instructors prefer this work to improve their students’ communication skills. In this group work, students can analyze and identify their mistakes, discuss different topics, present their posters, and practice their presentations along with their group partners. This method also urges students to cooperate, take responsibility, and work with stronger and high-level students. In this group work, there can be created a real and natural language atmosphere.

Role play is considered another crucial communicative method and it is mostly connected to real life and real contexts, so students can interact and work easily. This is because, all scenarios and contents are taken from their own life and experiences. In the role play, students have to interact with different contexts like job interviews, travel conversations, business related conversations, customer services and other important contexts. In addition, this technique helps learners to acquire the spoken language better and quickly.

Another crucial activity is information-gap, it is considered a real need for interaction. For example, there are two students whose knowledge is totally different for the one topic. At that time, one of them will share the information which he learned and another one can complete his gap. By doing this activity, both students can acquire the language and data efficiently and they

can also save their time. These activities are quite useful since students need to speak and interact with each other with a clear and real purpose.

In higher education, debates and discussions are very important, as they create opportunity for students to express their ideas and share their thoughts within a whole group and in front of the big audience. Discussions also enhance students' competence, confidence and overcome their shyness and fear which are quite essential especially in their personal and academic life. Furthermore, these tasks develop and shape their critical thinking, fluency, and oral skills

The role of communicative methods in improving learning outcomes

Communicative methods are considered the most crucial part of learning English and teaching it as they can open ways to make the lessons more interactive, active, student-oriented, meaningful and contextual. First of all, with these activities can be involved and appealed easily to take part in the group, pair work and some discussions. In shortly, it enhances students' involvement. During the class, they are not anymore just the listeners rather they are the active participants and lesson's one part. It gives them better attention and stronger motivation.

Secondly, communicative methods can help learners to integrate all four main skills in one method. This is because, in real communication, speaking, writing, reading, and listening are often used together. For instance, students can read one article which was taken from journals and magazines, then they might take notes from some important places in order to express their speeches to their partners. Also, they might listen to some natural conversations which are held on YouTube and TVs and then they share their acquired knowledge with their friends and their closed ones in English. This technique works better especially, if the students are auditory learners.

Thirdly, by applying the communicative teaching, teachers can urge learners to be more confident and motivated and it definitely increases their confidence, if the classroom is supportive and less strict on the accuracy. At that time, learner does not worry about making mistakes rather they pay attention a lot the process of communication and acquiring the language.

Conclusion

In conclusion, abovementioned communicative methods play an important role in teaching English and explaining it to the students, as it is connected to their life and daily tasks. They create a real English atmosphere in this way, students feel like they are in the center of native environment. Students also see the English subject a means of practicing language with enjoyment, not the limited version of practicing the language with rules and memorization techniques. With the help of pair work, group work, role play, debates and discussions, information-gap tasks, along with presentations, students grow their activeness, confidence, and their competence in applying the English.

Communicative teaching methods not only support the education's quality, but also help the learners to develop their independence, interaction, practical language use, and their critical thinking. Although some classroom difficulties may appear, these can be reduced through careful planning, clear support, and flexible teaching. For this reason, communicative methods should be viewed as one of the most effective tools for improving English language teaching in higher education.

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